

Contribution of Artificial and Emotional Intelligence to Sports Performance of Players in Technological Era

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ABSTRACT. The purpose of the present research was to determine the extent to which artificial and emotional intelligence affected the sporting performance of players in today era. The research methodology was based on a quantitative research approach. Survey research design was employed for

this study. Multi-game club players from the districts of Faisalabad and Sargodha were considered the population of the study. The sample size comprised of 550 club players belonging to both Districts (Faisalabad and Sargodha). To gather the survey data, a self-administered questionnaire was employed using a five-point Likert scale. Pilot testing was done to refine the scale and collected the data from 40 subjects to precede the results in this regard. Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation), Pearson's correlation analysis, and multiple regression analysis employed to analyze the collected data and draw the results, whereas, SPSS V-26 software was used to edit the collected survey data and further analysis. The significance level was set at the 0.05 value. The findings of correlation analysis revealed highly significant and positive relationships of artificial intelligence and emotional intelligence with the sport performance of players. The results of multiple regression analysis indicated significant variance of artificial intelligence and emotional intelligence in the sports performance of players. Research implications implied that the artificial intelligence component with emotional intelligence may excel the technical capabilities and emotional stability of the players enhancing a more precise and adaptive sports culture in Pakistani sports. It was recommended that the Pakistani sports clubs should integrate with the use of modern artificial intelligence technologies and emotional intelligence trainings in order to improve the sports performance of players.

INTRODUCTION

Sports is a word used to explain competitive and entertaining actions someone can execute individually or in unison with other people to enhance the mental and physical abilities of an individual (Sakar, 2022). Sports have always been important in establishing identities influencing civilizations, and advancing psychological and physical health. The prior research highlighted the positive effect of sports on youth development, global and sustainable development, community and social development, and world peace. Due to its commercialization and expansion as a distinct industry that generated affluent players' sports may also significantly affect a nation's economy (Meng et al., 2024).

Sport has a direct connection to human history (Glushchenko, 2023). A history of sports that spans thousands of years and several civilizations, empires, and periods is inextricably linked to the development of human civilization. The Olympic Games are one of the most important athletic events in the world because of their rich history and profound influence. From the ancient Greek Games to the modern International Olympic Games, the Olympic Games have changed throughout thousands of years (Zhou, 2023).

For the last 20 years, Pakistan's top players have often found it difficult to compete internationally and the country's success in top-tier players' events is inconsistent with its population size and economic foundation. The success of Pakistan in squash, hockey and cricket is a reminder of the colonial history of the country (Ali et al., 2023). However, at the present, overall Pakistani sports did not get recognition at international arenas in the technological era. The causes behind it may be the advancement of modern techniques or the latest usage of mechanical work is involved such as artificial and emotional intelligence.

The term artificial intelligence (AI) was first used in the 1950s and it is used to describe the concept of creating robots that can perform the activities that humans carry out normally (Schwendicke et al., 2020). The capacity of robots to do intellectual tasks similar to those of humans is a typical definition of artificial intelligence. They may involve such an improvement of physiological processes where diverse actions are involved including displacement and manipulation of objects, perception, and interpretation of sensory data, understanding and responding to the environment, problem analysis and decisions developing innovative solutions, and making informed decisions (Benbya et al., 2020). The core of the supersonic growth of new intelligence surveillance and its solutions is the state-of-the-art AI infrastructure without which the development of these technologies could not have grown so effectively (Xu, 2021).

AI is used everywhere in sports in worldwide. To illustrate, computers used wearable sensors and cameras that took precise physiological information of the players during practice and competition. According to Wei et al., (2021), the use of AI in designing sports training and teaching systems within colleges could satisfy the requirements of different students, reach the objective of personalized customized service development, and provide a background of AI development in general in sports services. Analyzing this data with the use of AI technology can assist coaches in coming up with the most effective game plan besides assist them in coming up with individual training routines to players (Wei et al., 2021).

Sport has always been a resonant activity as it gives people a chance to make the most out of their physical performance and play a game in competition with others. Nevertheless, the way AI is being implemented in games is changing the nature of sports and the player performance thresholds (Xu, 2021). AI and sports science together increased in performance of the players, reduced the chances of injury, and promoted the formulation of superior stratagem in sports. AI can also perform biomechanical assessments by paying close attention to their movements and thereby helping sports to enhance their practices (Ding, 2019).

The AI technology has evolved immensely within recent years and it is currently making a massive impact on a variety of industries. It was critical to conduct a thorough analysis of AI's ramifications taking into account both the potential and difficulties it poses, as it continues to transform the world of international sports (Javed et al., 2024). AI has been used to change sports in ways that are beyond our present understanding and are many and immeasurable. Recently, AI has been used to define every aspect of sports at every level possible enabling the transformation of data and analysis and transforming the way that games are planned and executed on the field (Molavian et al., 2023).

In order to improve the experience of players, coaches, and spectators during the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, AI has focused on delivering top-notch technological integrations. As the internet and technology continued to advance more and more academics studying sports are examining the impact of AI on changing people's long-term employment and lifestyle in the future and whether it will have an effect on sports training or not (Gajendra, 2023). Nonetheless, it is anticipated that as technology advances and new advancements are made artificial intelligence will permeate every aspect of sports and bring about significant changes (Atasoy et al., 2021).

Sports training involved AI to deliver customized training plans and instant feedback to players and coaches to boost the efficiency of every activity to every individual person (Mohammed et al., 2024). As a consequence of AI-generated competition analysis, coaches may quickly search through a vast array of new talents that players will contribute to their teams and readily access the growth via more efficient training regimens that assess all areas of players' performance. For instance knowing when a players' performance starts to decline would make it simpler to adjust training plans (Atasoy et al., 2021).

In sports training, AI has been deployed to give players and coaches individualized training plans and instantaneous feedback enhancing the effectiveness of that activity at an individual level (Mohammed et al., 2024). As a consequence of AI-generated competition analysis, coaches may quickly search through a vast array of new talents that players will contribute to their teams and readily access the growth via more efficient training regimens that assess both the qualitative and quantitative components of their players. For instance, knowing when a players' performance starts to decline would make it simpler to adjust training plans (Atasoy et al., 2021).

AI may be used to develop training plans to help players become better as well as to monitor health and avoid injuries (Wei et al., 2021). AI is having a significant influence on training and strategy both before and during a game. Additionally, AI and machine learning are helping game judges, referees, and

umpires make wise choices. The third umpire in cricket employed AI-driven visualization to help the umpire make decisions when the human eye is unable to detect even the smallest millimeter-level variations or split seconds (Gajendra, 2023).

On the other hand, Shahan, Ali, and Rasool (2023) defined emotional intelligence (EI) as the congenital capacity in an individual to control and regulated oneself or others and weigh the consideration of feelings of other people and used their feelings and those of other people as a guide to their behaviors and thoughts. The EI involved using emotions to inform thinking and actions due to learning to be sensitive to and regulate their feelings and the feelings of others (Cakiroglu, 2021).

Emotions influenced motivation, action, perceived, cognition, personal feeling, and decision making and could help facilitate or hinder performance in sports or sporting activities (Shahan et al., 2023). The effect of sport on the levels of EI was significant since sports are characterized by a reasonable degree of influence of sporting activities due to their nature and performance of participants, and perhaps an association exists between sport and development of EI (Stan et al., 2022). The engagement of players in the sport affected their EI. Sports may contribute to the development of emotion regulation abilities and effective emotion regulation methods positively influence the EI of players.

Emotions can be either positive or negative regarding sports performance in that they influenced motivation, behavior, perception, cognition, personal feelings, and decision-making process (Shahan et al., 2023). The effect of sports on EI levels was great after taking into account the nature of sports and their participants demonstrating them which suggested the existence of a potential correlation between sports and emotional intelligence development (Stan et al., 2022). Sports participation affected players' emotional intelligence (EI) and exercise may improve emotional regulation skills. Furthermore, successful emotion management strategies have a positive influence on EI. In sports, AI has become a game-changing technology that improves player performance and changes the sports environment. Pakistani players are underappreciated on both national and international levels due to the unrealized potential of AI and AI-driven technologies in sports which discouraged player's performance from being optimized (Tahir et al., 2022).

EI is the capability to recognize, understand, and deal effectively with personal and other people emotions to facilitate productive relationships and behaviors, and thinking (Robres et al., 2023). The secret to maximizing your potential, achieving success and performing at your best is EI. Despite their skills and potential, Pakistani sportsmen often did poorly in international sporting events. This poor performance might be caused in part by players' lack of

emotional intelligence (Fayyaz et al., 2018). Players who possessed emotional intelligence can control their emotions, maintain focus, and perform well under pressure. However, there is a dearth of study on Pakistani players' EI specifically with their sports performance (Mazhar et al., 2021).

The developments in science and technology shaped the evolution of sports as well as their influences. AI incorporation into sports has significantly changed the sports sector in recent years but there are still a number of obstacles to overcome before its full potential can be realized (Javed et al., 2024). From speech recognition systems to route-finding apps, AI and EI have permeated our everyday life. AI is being extensively used by scientists in different fields like sports (Kaya, 2023).

AI has revolutionized the sports sector in a number of ways and brought about many advantages. But its use also brought up serious issues with safety and fairness in sports (Ding, 2019). The integrated use of AI in players' performance has not been thoroughly examined in prior study (Wei et al., 2021). Even if artificial intelligence is being used in sports more, players' performance has to be improved via increased understanding and use of AI (Rahmani et al., 2024).

EI is now receiving a growing awareness of having a part in the performance of individuals in various kinds of sports (Gkora & Driga, 2023). Though, its influence on a players' performance under extreme pressure is still poorly understood. EI is essential for comprehending team dynamics, player motivation, and emotional well-being (Montenegro et al., 2024).

Past research emphasized that EI, despite its rising popularity, appeared to be an attribute that contributed to developing certain abilities and forecasting better sports performance results (Montenegro-Bonilla et al., 2024). This motivated coaches, professionals, psychologists, and cross-functional teams to learn the EI for developing the sports performance of players (Aronen et al., 2021).

Furthermore, it was not well understood how much EI influenced players' performance outcomes in conjunction with other psychological variables including empathy, resilience, and focus (Mazhar et al., 2021). When EI is not prioritized in sports, players struggled to utilize their full potential and found purpose in their athletic pursuits which results in underachievement, stagnation, and a lack of fulfillment (Lepers et al., 2025).

Although, the benefits of AI and EI are undeniable, these constructs has not been deeply investigated in terms of its scope of influence on sports performance in Pakistani preview. The existing research sought to examine the contributions of AI and EI to players' performance to understand the technological innovation in AI and emotional regulation using EI and can be

used to train the players, develop their game plans, and build their mental strengths. This study addressed the aim of unveiling a possible synergy between AI and EI with respect to recognizing the role of AI and EI in the technological age regarding the optimal sports performance of players.

OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

The following objectives of the study were generated from the existing literature:

- i.** To access the extent of the applications about knowledge and use of artificial intelligence in sports.
- ii.** To investigate the strategies to develop the emotional intelligence enhancing performance, achievement, and success in sports.
- iii.** To examine the relationship between artificial intelligence and sports performance of the players.
- iv.** To find out the association between emotional intelligence and sports performance of the players.
- v.** To determine the effect of artificial intelligence and emotional intelligence on sports performance of the players.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Based on the gaps identified in the present literature, the following research questions were formulated:

- RQ 1:** What is the extent of the applications about knowledge and use of artificial intelligence in sports?
- RQ 2:** What strategies are to be needed to develop emotional intelligence to enhance performance, achievement, and success in sports?
- RQ 3:** What is the relationship between artificial intelligence and sports performance of the players?
- RQ 4:** What is the association between emotional intelligence and sports performance of the players?
- RQ 5:** What is the effect of artificial intelligence and emotional intelligence on the sports performance of players?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The hypotheses for the present research were proposed to answer the research questions:

- Ha1:** There is significant relationship between artificial intelligence and sports performance of the players.

Ha2: There is significant association between emotional intelligence and sports performance of the players.

Ha3: There is significant effect of artificial intelligence and emotional intelligence on the sports performance of players.

METHODOLOGY

A quantitative research method utilizing a survey research design was employed in this study. The population of the present research consisted of 3100 players from various clubs belonging to Faisalabad and Sargodha. Simple random sampling was used since each population member would have an equal and fair opportunity to be chosen in the study increasing the degree of neutrality and reliability of the results. The sample size was consisted of 550 players belonging to Faisalabad and Sargodha districts. Self-administered questionnaire was used as the research instrument for the present study.

A pilot study was carried out to evaluate the efficacy of the questionnaire used to gather data from a sample of 40 club players in Faisalabad. The survey questionnaire was statistically validated using SPSS V-26 to ensure its reliability and validity. Sample adequacy was measured by Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) to infer validity and the Bartlett test of sphericity was used to confirm the adequacy of factor analysis. Moreover, Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was measured to determine internal consistency with scores above 0.7 giving acceptable levels of reliability. After the pilot testing, it was found that all variables fulfilled the primarily and satisfactory requirements to be need to refine the instrument. After refine the scale, 550 questionnaires were distributed among the respondents of Faisalabad and Sargodha districts as the part of the population to collect data from the sports clubs. However, 511 respondents returned the filled survey questionnaires back.

After the data collection, to examine the relationships among variables, correlation analysis was conducted using Pearson's correlation analysis. Additionally, multiple regression analysis was used to investigate the variance of the independent variables in the outcome variable.

RESULTS

Pearson's correlation analysis, multiple regression analysis, and SPSS software were utilized to analyze the results of the collected survey data. The results section summarized the main conclusions and provided a thorough overview of the study's results emphasizing the usefulness of incorporating AI and EI into players' performances.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

The Pearson's correlation coefficient which ranged from -1 to 1 is a statistical tool used to quantify the association between two variables. The straight-line equation may represent two variables and the two variables are positively associated as shown by the numerical value of 1. Despite having a negative correlation, the two variables may also be represented by a linear equation as seen by the coefficient value of -1. The two variables have a linear connection that is closer to zero when the coefficient's absolute value is near zero and larger when the coefficient's absolute value is near one.

Table 1: Relationship of Artificial Intelligence with Sports Performance of Players (n-511)

Variables		Health management	Injury Prediction	Wearable Devices	Skill Development	Sports Performance
Health Management	Pearson Correlation	-				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
Injury Prediction	Pearson Correlation	.567**	-			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000				
Wearable Devices	Pearson Correlation	.559**	.610**	-		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000			
Skill Development	Pearson Correlation	.581**	.599**	.613**	-	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		
Sports Performance	Pearson Correlation	.536**	.566**	.609**	.609**	-
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Health management as a sub-variable of AI was significantly correlated with the sports performance of players ($r = .536, p = 0.001$) as displayed in Table 1. The Pearson's correlation between AI and the sports performance of players revealed a strong enough. The result from the correlation analysis showed that health management has a positive and moderate relationship with the sports performance of players. The association between artificial intelligence and sports performance was found to be highly significant.

The relationship between AI and sports performance of players was found to be strong enough. Injury prediction as a sub-variable of artificial intelligence was significantly correlated with the sports performance of players ($r = .566, p = 0.001$). The relationship between artificial intelligence and sports performance was found to be highly significant.

The results showed a substantial relationship between sports performance of players and wearable technology with Pearson's correlation value ($r = .609, p = 0.001$). The Pearson's correlation criteria classified this number as strong indicating a strong relationship. This important result which is highlighted supported the robust relationship shown in the data and can be shown in Table 1.

According to the findings of correlation analysis, skill development and sports performance of players are positively correlated. Thus, Table 1 demonstrated that skill development has a highly significant relationship with sports performance of players ($r = .609, p = 0.001$). The correlation was strong; thus, the results implied a strong correlation between players' improved sports performance and skill development advancements.

Table 2: Relationship of Emotional Intelligence with Sports Performance of Players (n-511)

Variables		Self-Awareness	Self-Regulation	Focus	Empathy	Sports Performance
Self-Awareness	Pearson Correlation	-				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
Self-Regulation	Pearson Correlation	.625**	-			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000				
Focus	Pearson Correlation	.579**	.659**	-		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000			
Empathy	Pearson Correlation	.493**	.571**	.590*	-	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		
Sports Performance	Pearson Correlation	.577**	.627**	.572*	.480**	-
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Self-awareness as a sub-variable of EI was significantly correlated with the sports performance of players ($r = .577, p = 0.001$) as displayed in Table 2. The Pearson's correlation between EI and the sports performance of players revealed a strong enough. The results from the correlation analysis showed that self-awareness has a positive and moderate relationship with the sports performance of players. The association between EI and sports performance was found to be highly significant.

The relationship between EI and the sports performance of players was found to be highly Significant. Self-regulation as a sub-variable of emotional intelligence was significantly correlated with the sports performance of players ($r = .625, p = 0.001$). The results from the correlation analysis showed that self-regulation has a positive relationship with the sports performance of players.

The correlation analysis's findings focused as a sub-variable of emotional intelligence and sports performance are strongly positively correlated. Results demonstrated that focus has a highly significant relationship with sports performance of players ($r = .572, p = 0.001$). Thus, the results implied a strong positive correlation between focus as a sub variable of EI and sports performance of players.

Empathy as a sub-variable of emotional intelligence was significantly correlated with the sports performance of players ($r = .480, p = 0.001$) as displayed in Table 2. The results from the correlation analysis showed that empathy has a positive and moderate relationship with the sports performance of players. The association between EI and sports performance was found to be highly significant.

MULTIPLE REGRESSION ANALYSIS

The present research implied multiple regression analysis to examine the effect of artificial intelligence and emotional intelligence on the sports performance of players. To know the variance of predictor factors in outcome variables, multiple regression analysis was used.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics (n-511)

Constructs	Mean	Std. Deviation
Sports Performance of Players	17.25	5.350
Artificial Intelligence	60.53	15.606
Emotional Intelligence	56.71	15.066

A multiple regression analysis was employed to investigate the effect of artificial intelligence (AI) and emotional intelligence (EI) on players' sports performance. The degree of variation between individual scores was suggested by the average score of 17.25 with a standard deviation (SD) of 5.350 for sports performance; a higher mean score of 60.53 with a standard deviation of 15.606 for AI indicated greater variability among participants, whereas, a mean score of 56.71 with an SD of 15.066 indicated a similar level of variation within the dataset as indicated in Table 3.

Table 4: Results of Model Summary (n-511)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.732a	.536	.530	3.650	1.858

a. Predictors: (Constant), Emotional Intelligence, Artificial Intelligence
b. Dependent Variable: Sports Performance

The results showed that the R square value was 536 and the adjusted R-squared value was 530 indicating the data was statistically significant as defined in Table 4. Artificial intelligence and emotional intelligence are the independent factors that accounted for 53% of the variation in sports performance according to the adjusted R-square (R^2) value of 0.530. In addition, the Durbin-Watson statistic was found to be 1.858 and the standard error of the estimate was found 3.650.

Table 5: ANOVA Results

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7832.445	2	3916.222	293.992	.000
	Residual	6766.991	508	13.321		
	Total	14599.436	510			

a. Dependent Variable: Sports Performance
b. Predictors: (Constant), Emotional Intelligence, Artificial Intelligence

The ANOVA findings showed statistical significance with $F(2,508)=293.99$ and $p =0.001$ as shown in Table 5. This demonstrated that AI and EI predictors significantly affected the sports performance of players. This highlighted that emotional intelligence and AI-driven insights can enhance players' ability to manage stress and improve overall performance in high-pressure situations.

Table 6: Results of Coefficients (n-511)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	1.375	.674		2.039	.042		
Artificial Intelligence	.148	.017	.432	8.886	.000	.387	2.587
Emotional Intelligence	.122	.017	.343	7.067	.000	.387	2.587

a. Dependent Variable: Sports Performance

The results revealed that artificial intelligence ($\beta = .432, t = 8.886, p = .001$) and emotional intelligence ($\beta = .343, t = 7.067, p = .001$) significantly had effect on the sports performance of the players. These values indicated highly significant results for both variables. The collinearity data showed no multicollinearity existed among the predictors and had the acceptable ranges as shown in Table 6.

DISCUSSION

The fact found in this investigation reinforced the work by other researchers in the field and gave further indication of the interrelationship between AI, EI and sports performance of players. Health management, particularly the sub-variable of AI an increasingly significant element for enhancing sports performance of players. AI has the potential to significantly affect various aspects of coaching and team sports participation, including injury monitoring, team and individual health, and safety (Munoz et al., 2024). AI in health management has allowed the players to perform better due to more effective training plans, physiological condition monitoring, and injury prevention.

The research indicated that AI could ensure safer and more targeted treatment for players by tracking key health markers and making predictions about potential illnesses, thereby, offering more precise care and enhancing player performance (Rahmani et al., 2024). Previous research supported the application of AI technologies leads to a serious growth in the performance of sportsmen, particularly, through injury prevention and optimal training programs (Javed et al., 2024). Such alterations in the ways of managing health ensured that players have preserved an excellent shape and this is associated with their enhanced success in sports.

The correlation analysis was applied in order to find out the association between AI-based health management and sports performance. The results indicated that two factors were significantly correlated. Herold et al., (2019) affirmed that AI-based health management strategies are rapidly becoming invaluable assets to sports teams guaranteeing that players healed fully and performed at their optimum abilities again. This implied that as such health management systems powered by AI become more efficient; it is possible to notice a distinctive escalation in sports performance by players. The study emphasized the how the capacity of AI to constantly check and alter health-related information of each player enhances their fitness and overall performance in legally competitive sports conditions (Omarov et al., 2024).

AI is instrumental in health management and injury prevention and has a strong relationship with the sports performance of players (Rahmani et al., 2024). The study also indicated that the correlation between AI and sports performance was considerably high, indicating that the idea that AI would assist in the management of health in real-life conditions was meaningful. Athlete performance has been greatly improved by AI, especially, in training optimization and prevention of injuries (Javed et al., 2024).

To sum up, AI is a critical technology in the rehabilitation of sports because it enabled injuries to be tracked, develops individualized rehabilitation programs and assessments (Macho et al., 2021). When in the process of rehabilitation, AI reduced the likelihood of reinjury and the likelihood that players can re-enter the competition arena and in an ideal shape (Sirawattana & Poolsamra, 2024). The growth in this direction will most likely lead to a long-term effect on sports by providing rehabilitation with a more scientific base and a more organized structure.

By encompassing AI in sport science, sports scientists and coaches can engage in making data-driven choices that influenced the direct training and recovery of players (Zeng et al., 2021). Based on the findings, additional support and research on AI health management technologies are essential to promote players in all types of sports. This invention has the capability of revolutionizing performance optimization. Using diverse technological applications, the current research indicated how AI can significantly improve sporting performance by respective players and the fact that they needed it. The findings of the study established a significant association between the improvement of the sports activities and the application of AI in several aspects such as the improvement of skills, injury forecasting, and wellbeing.

With the methods of AI, it is possible to measure the physical condition of players correctly and obtain significant information about potential injuries in advance, in order to intervene as quickly as possible (Mateus et al., 2024). Health management systems based on AI can also help to streamline recovery,

personalize training regimes, and enhance specific skills. In general, the results showed that AI-powered technologies not only changed sports science but also are critical in enhancing player performance which guaranteed greater consistency and success in their respective sports.

Use of AI in injury prevention and health management is among the most promising applications of AI in sports. AI systems can help understand when an injury is likely to happen and which preventative measures can be taken by constantly observing the biomechanical and physiological data of the players. Such a preventive strategy can lower the likelihood of an athlete's injury by large margins and prolong their careers (Najjar, 2023). Wearable technology is a sub-variable that has been proven to affect sports performance greatly (Mateus et al., 2025). There was a strong positive relationship between wearable technology and sports performance existed and that explained why AI can be used to make players to perform better in their field of sport (Saeed et al., 2025).

Wearable technology has used to provide real-time physical condition data on players making it an essential part of optimizing sports performance. Another study supported that the application of wearable technology and analytics on performance optimization such as players subjective exertional weariness, mobility profile, hydration status, sleep, heart health, and SmO₂ in a return-to-play format followed significant injury (Seckin et al., 2023). The physiological and metabolic profiles of players have also been monitored with wearable sensors. To make informed adjustments during practice and game, it allowed players to monitor such variables as speed, heart rate, and efficiency of movement. In this way, players can fully achieve their performance, reduce the possibility of an injury, and also make evidence-based decisions to further develop their total skill set (Chidambaram et al., 2022).

The findings of the correlation research pointed out to the existence of a positive relationship between the development of skills of the players and sports results. Modern technology and skill training research on sports provided the key to the mystery of sports development, improving the scientific level of sports training having a great effect on the sports improvement of players and continuously contributing to the scientific level of sports training (Lin & Wang 2024). An improvement in competition outcomes was achieved when some of the sporting abilities were cultivated through target-specific training with the help of AI (Bodemer, 2023). It was the positive correlation that demonstrated the importance of the consistent improvement of skill through AI towards achieving long-term success in sports.

Players' success was significantly affected by their ability to regulate their emotions and maintain mental toughness as seen by the substantial correlation between emotional intelligence and sports performance.

According to Balk & Englert (2020), the Pearson's correlation between emotional intelligence and sports performance of players was found in a strong range.

The low EI allowed players to cope with pressure and make better decisions since they can control stress, remain motivated and have a positive attitude. High emotional intelligence is also likely to enhance the interpersonal skills of players that fostered communication and cooperation and enhanced performance further. Players' sport performance had a strong relation with the self-awareness sub-variable of EI. The findings of this study substantiated that there was a positive correlation between the self-awareness of players and sports performance (Cowden, 2020).

Due to being a subset of EI, self-awareness allowed sportsmen to determine their strengths and weaknesses in order to focus on them in the competition (Cahyo et al., 2022). This knowledge can help the players to maintain a stable emotional status as without it, the negative feelings would prevent them to operate efficiently in a pressure situation. Players who were self-aware can bend and accepted negative feedback and this factor encouraged continuous development and enhanced performance in sports in general (Kopp & Jekauc, 2018).

There was a significant correlation observed between sports performance of the players and self-regulation. Prior research has established that self-regulation played an important role related to the performance and overall well-being of players (Balk & Englert, 2020). Self-regulation which referred to the ability of any athlete to control feelings, ideas, and actions under difficult situations was one of the most significant elements of emotional intelligence.

Improving sports performance required the capacity to control impulses, remain composed under duress, and stay focused (Popovych et al., 2021). Strong self-control enables players to bounce back from setbacks fast, remained focused on their training and objectives, and performed consistently. Players can enhance their performance on the field, adjust to tactical adjustments, and maintain motivation throughout a game or season by managing their emotional reactions (Trotter et al., 2021).

According to the correlation analysis, sports performance and focus, a sub-variable of EI, were strongly positively correlated. According to Sepdanius et al. (2024), the relationship between focus as a sub-variable of emotional intelligence and sports performance of players revealed a strong enough. High-attention players were better able to concentrate, ignore outside distractions, and remain committed to the work at hand especially during crucial competitive moments (Singh & Wulf, 2022). Players can perform abilities more successfully, make wiser judgments, and adjust to the shifting game dynamics

because to their increased capacity for concentration. As an athlete's attention increased, so did their performance, according to the positive connection, underscoring the critical role EI played in maximizing sports performance of players (Zhuravleva & Aiken, 2023). The correlation results showed that sports performance and empathy which was an important part of EI were significantly correlated. In sports by developing stronger emotional tied with team members, empathy can make the players more mentally tough, thus improving their performance in the competition (Sepdanius et al., 2024).

Players with high levels of empathy were even more sensitive to the emotional needs of their teammates and this facilitates their better collaboration and communication in the playing field. Players should be able to guide their teammates through rough patches because of their emotional intelligence, thus enhancing team spirit and cohesion (Behm & Carter, 2021). Even though, empathy might not significantly affect personal skills and physical performance, it is more than probable that sports success is highly predisposed to the tendency to enhance team relations and generate an encouraging environment. Researchers have determined quantitative estimates of independent and interaction effects of AI and EI contribution to sports performance using multiple regression analysis. The combination of these factors allowed researchers to demonstrate how AI and EI, in combination, played a better role, and how they influence the success of sports teams.

The interaction of AI and EI significantly influenced the level of sports performance in players. Whilst EI allowed players to manage emotions better, became more resilient and maintained their mental sharpness in stress, AI enhanced their performance through providing data-driven feedback, streamlining training routines, and promoting injury prevention (Montenegro-Bonilla et al., 2024). The two components were in their ideal aspects as they enhanced the mental strength and physical capabilities that later lead to enhanced performance in competitive sports.

EI is very important in enhancing the performance in sport since it allowed players to be able to understand their emotions and learned to manage them effectively. Individuals who have high EI are also in a better position to decide and act calmly in stressful situations that would encourage resilience in competition. Additionally, emotional awareness with AI predictions enabled players to make more informed decisions, leading to a strategic advantage during the competition (Montenegro-Bonilla et al., 2024). Moreover, more emotionally intelligent athletes were not only more sympathetic himself but also more capable of handling interpersonal dynamics contributed to better collaboration and communication. Players with a strong EI can also be resilient and maintain elite performance status even in stressful environments, simply

because they knew how to manage stress and remain motivated (Popovych et al., 2021).

AI has a tremendous influence on the performance of players because it was based on the analysis of data to improve the strategy, receive the maximum during the training process, and avoid injuries (Musat et al., 2024). Further advancements in AI technology in recent years have significant effect on numerous sports industries and players' performance in sports (Saeed et al., 2025).

AI systems assessed biomechanics, movements, and general performance of players in order to facilitate their skills growth and deliver individual feedback. It also prevented injuries by monitoring the health of the players and identifying potential harm with predictive analytics (Musat et al., 2024). AI can also be utilized to assess the strategy of opponents, and this aspect assisted coaches and sportsmen in designing more efficient game strategies. Despite these aspects in all considerations, artificial intelligence enhanced the strategic and physical elements of sports allowing players to engage in their best (Atasoy et al., 2021).

CONCLUSION

The correlation analysis found significant relationships between AI and sports performance of players which meant that AI tools enhanced the sports performance of the players. Prediction of injuries and health management relied on AI since it was possible to analyze performance data on the players and determined trends and predicted risks. This allowed intervening in time reducing the risk of injuries and an assurance to players that they have better physical health. EI as demonstrated by the strong correlation with sports performance played an imperative role in influencing sports performance by enabling players to adequately manage their emotions in a way that enhanced focus and attention during competition. The synergistic effect of AI and EI placed a strong emphasis on their importance in performance optimization and suggested that both AI technology and EI regulation are essential to maximize sports performance of players.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings indicated that AI was a significant factor in enhancing sports performance in terms of health management, injury prediction, and skill development. As a result of the findings, the concept of AI in health management systems should be further influenced in favor of promoting physical health and injury prevention. Moreover, AI-based systems must be used in skill development and injury prediction to maximize performance and minimize training risks.

In view of the findings, it is recommended that the wearable technologies should be incorporated into the usual training sessions of club players because this will allow for monitoring and developing physical performance more effectively. Sports teams in Pakistan should aim at investing in AI-powered systems to improve performance, injury forecasting, and health tracking as the technology will play a constructive role in the future development of all sports.

Trainers, psychologists and mentors should implement programs of self-awareness, emotional management and communication to keep the athlete focused and in control. Future sports programs should include dedicated attention exercises and formal empathy-building activities to formally improve players' interpersonal skills on the field.

Pakistan needs to encourage a more potent sports policy that should focus not only on the application of AI technology but also on the development of EI among players.

A structure of sports federations, government agencies, and privately organized bodies should exist to deal with the aspects of both the mental and physical training. This should entail the establishment of specialized centers of excellence where mental training programs founded on EI are applied alongside AI-based technologies. In this way, Pakistan should enhance its international sport events by helping to build the players and teams emotionally and physically ready to participate in these international events.

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